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 POSITIVE

Funded by
the European Union

THE **POSITIVE** IMPACT CHALLENGE **PLAYBOOK**

A TOOL TO SUPPORT DIGITAL INNOVATION
IN SOCIAL BUSINESSES

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1. INTRODUCTION

CONNECTING **DIGITAL** AND
SOCIAL INNOVATION

POSITIVE PROJECT

The POSITIVE project, funded by the European Union under the HORIZON EUROPE Programme, aims to **bridge the gap between social and digital technology innovation ecosystems**, which often operate in isolation.

The project involves **six partners from Italy, Germany, and Lithuania**, representing both the social and tech innovation sectors:

- **Social innovation:** Grünhof - GH (GER), Lithuanian Social Business Association - LiSVA (LIT), Trentino Social Tank - TST (ITA).
- **Tech innovation:** Fondazione Hub Innovazione Trentino - HIT (ITA), Lithuanian Innovation Centre - LIC (LIT), Steinbeis Europa Zentrum - SEZ (GER).

POSITIVE aims to **boost collaboration and understanding** between these two ecosystems, which currently isn't optimal: on one side, social innovation actors face challenges such as limited entrepreneurial skills and difficulties with digitizing their services; on the other side, technology innovation and business support organizations also often misunderstand the specific scope and needs of social entrepreneurship.

To tackle these challenges, the POSITIVE project focuses on:

AWARENESS RAISING AND CAPACITY BUILDING

The project promotes the benefits of social innovation within the digital technology sector and provides training to help both social and tech innovators understand each other's fields, creating a more inclusive innovation environment.

FOSTERING OPEN INNOVATION

The project promotes Open Innovation Contest a.k.a. "Challenges" in Germany, Italy, and Lithuania, to help social innovation actors digitize their products and services and discover new business opportunities by absorbing knowledge and skills from digital tech actors.

PROMOTE CROSS-FERTILIZATION AND NEW POLICIES

The project connects social and technology innovation ecosystems at both regional and European levels through networking, knowledge exchange and policy recommendations.

[CHECK OUT THE PROJECT'S WEBSITE HERE!](#)

FROM DIGITAL INNOVATION...

Digital innovation involves leveraging digital technologies to create new or enhanced products, services, or processes, reshaping business operations. For SMEs - Small and Medium Enterprises (including, potentially, social innovation actors), this innovation is crucial as it boosts efficiency, improves customer experiences, and uncovers new market opportunities. By integrating digital tools, SMEs can streamline their operations, stay competitive, and respond swiftly to market changes, thereby fostering growth and enhancing profitability in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

...TO SOCIAL INNOVATION

Social innovation involves creating new solutions to tackle social challenges like climate change and inequality. Social innovators are those who drive these changes, including social entrepreneurs who develop impactful projects and organizations that support them, such as impact investors and philanthropic groups. Their work aims to improve society by addressing pressing issues through innovative approaches.

LEVERAGING OPEN INNOVATION

Open Innovation has been utilized worldwide to **connect innovation players and ecosystems**. Along with that, Innovation Contests and Challenges have been utilized to enable Open Innovation in an agile manner and within short time frames. One example of Innovation Contest is the UX Challenge (or “user experience” Challenge). The UX Challenge is an **Open Innovation Contest** designed to accelerate **research-industry knowledge transfer** and **support digital product innovation in SMEs** by focusing on improving the user experience of digital products and services.

The format embeds **user-centered design** and **design thinking** activities into a one-week intensive program involving university students, digital companies and UX design professionals (including researchers) as co-innovators.

During the Challenge, teams of university students specializing in human-computer interaction, work to **test and redesign the usability and user experience of digital products and services** provided by a number of participating companies.

By enhancing the UX of these products, the Challenge aims to improve their ease of use, accessibility, and appeal, which can significantly boost market profitability and drive business growth.

THE POSITIVE IMPACT CHALLENGE

The POSITIVE Impact Challenge builds on the UX Challenge format with the extent of **boosting the digital innovation capabilities of social businesses and entrepreneurs**.

The POSITIVE Impact Challenge allows to connect social innovation actors with young digital innovators, researchers, and potential customers with the aim to **improve the user experience** and overall value of their products and services.

Through this collaborative process, participants co-design and improve **new product and service features and functionalities**, as well as concepts and business models, gaining valuable skills that prepare them to apply for innovation funding typically available to startups, SMEs, and researchers.

The POSITIVE Impact Challenge addresses the **need to increase digitization in the social economy sector**, which often falls behind other industries. Since social businesses rarely create tech products on their own, the POSITIVE Impact Challenge includes digital experts as mentors to ensure successful outcomes and strengthen connections within the innovation ecosystem.

2. OPEN INNOVATION AND INNOVATION CONTESTS

AN OVERVIEW OF KEY **CONCEPTS** AND
METHODOLOGICAL REFERENCES

OPEN INNOVATION - A FEW KEY TERMS

CHALLENGE

“**Innovation Challenges**” are initiatives focused on education, knowledge-sharing, training, and, ultimately, open innovation, typically organized by innovation intermediaries. They promote technology transfer and research-business collaboration, enabling companies to pursue product / service / process innovation. These Challenges are competitive, offering incentives to “problem solvers” who have engaged to develop viable solutions to the submitted problems or “**challenges**” presented by companies or other type of entities (e.g. public administration) “seeking” to absorb innovation contributions from the outside.

SEEKERS

“**Seekers**” are the beneficiary entities (e.g. SMEs or other enterprises, as well as public administrations) seeking to incorporate innovation input from external actors. They apply to participate to the Challenge with products / services / processes that will be analyzed and improved by teams of solvers. The number of seekers in a Challenge typically ranges from 3 to 10, based on resources and expected impact.

SOLVERS

“**Solvers**” are young talents (typically university students, including Ph.D. students) that have the competences and motivation to co-design solutions to the challenges submitted by the Seekers. In the POSITIVE Impact Challenge key competences include UX design, interaction design, and human-computer interaction. Therefore, solvers are normally computer scientists, designers, sociologists, psychologists, economists). Solvers work in teams of 4 to 6, each of which is matched with one seeker and challenge.

MENTORS

“**Mentors**” are experts in the Challenge domain, who can be a professional (e.g. a startup founder), a researcher, an university professor, depending on Challenge scope. Each team participating in the Challenge is assigned one mentor: the mentor helps and guides the team throughout the Challenge, offering advice and expertise. Although the mentor is not responsible for the team's results, s/he is a key resource for organizers as s/he can boost teams' operation capacity and Challenge results.

WHAT IS OPEN INNOVATION

Open Innovation occurs when a company or other entity (e.g. a public administration) collaborates with third parties, like clients or suppliers, to **find ideas and solutions for improving products and processes**. This collaborative approach is common in large enterprises due to their extensive research and development (R&D) resources. However, smaller entities such as SMEs face several challenges in its use, including limited financial resources, lack of innovation management skills, shorter time frames, and difficulties in partnering with academic institutions [1, 2, 3].

TOOLS FOR FOSTERING OPEN INNOVATION

Innovation prizes are a key tool for promoting Open Innovation: prizes reward advances in research and technology aimed at solving major social challenges. Traditionally offered by governments, innovation prizes are now also used by large companies to stimulate progress [1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

Innovation Contests and Challenges are competitive events where companies collaborate with students, researchers and technology experts. These events focus on developing practical solutions to industrial problems, such as new technologies or prototypes. Both innovation prizes and Challenges connect problem owners (seekers) with problem solvers, driving practical innovations that can benefit entire territories and the society as a whole [10].

ROLE OF INNOVATION INTERMEDIARIES

Innovation prizes, Contests, and Challenges are typically organized by innovation intermediaries. These organizations have strong expertise in innovation and intellectual property (IP) management and possess the capacity to engage effectively with both seekers and solvers.

UNDERSTANDING SOCIAL INNOVATION

Social innovation focuses on addressing social challenges through new services, products, or processes. It aims to create significant, transformative changes and provides systemic solutions that have a notable social impact. This type of innovation depends heavily on collective action, involving the collaboration of various stakeholders to achieve its goals [11].

CHALLENGES FOR SOCIAL ENTERPRISES

Social enterprises often encounter difficulties in adopting Open Innovation. Their limited budgets can restrict their ability to invest in R&D. Additionally, these organizations might view Open Innovation as a potential distraction from their core mission of promoting collective well-being. Moreover, the organizational culture in many social enterprises can be less open to external ideas, making it harder to integrate new approaches.

THE BENEFITS OF OPEN INNOVATION

Despite these challenges, Open Innovation can offer substantial benefits to social enterprises. By engaging with a diverse range of stakeholders and beneficiaries, these organizations can develop more effective solutions and significantly enhance their impact. Open Innovation allows social enterprises to tap into external perspectives and expertise, leading to more innovative and impactful outcomes [12].

EXAMPLE OF OPEN INNOVATION CONTEST: THE UX CHALLENGE

The UX Challenge is an open innovation initiative aimed at **helping companies enhance their digital products and services**. It connects companies developing digital products and services with experts to drive improvements to existing or newly launched product development projects through collaborative design and user-centered methods. During the Challenge, young talents such as university students **team up to develop viable solutions** and compete for a final prize; during the process they receive mentorship from UX design professionals and HCI researchers.

METHODOLOGY AND OUTPUTS

The UX Challenge resembles a one-week [Design Sprint](#) [13], a five-step process grounded in design thinking principles. This methodology guides teams through the creation and testing of prototypes of solutions, such as GUI - Graphical User Interface mockups, interface wireframes and interactive prototypes, which are also **tested with end-users**, according to user-centered design principles.

OUTCOMES

Outcomes of the Challenge are such as: i) industrialization of the developed prototypes; ii) further maturation of prototypes by means of activating internships / academic thesis with one or more solvers or establishing collaborations with mentors; iii) companies hiring solvers; iv) companies establishing innovation collaborations with mentors.

IMPACT OF OPEN INNOVATION CONTESTS

Open Innovation Contests typically impact on companies' innovation capability as a whole, e.g. in terms of: i) being capable of engaging in further open innovation processes; ii) learning benefits and feasibility of digital technologies and design thinking methods; iii) becoming aware of the need to upskill personnel or review new product/ service development processes.

This was partly demonstrated by the [200SMEchallenge project](#), which enabled seven European Innovation Agencies across Europe to **activate the UX Challenge**. The project involved nearly 200 European SMEs participating in a Randomized Controlled Trial (**RCT**) to assess the scheme's impact.

The project showed that companies participating in the UX Challenge as seekers (compared to those that did not participate - control group) **significantly boosted their understanding of design thinking and user-centered design (+19%)**. Their practical ability to apply these methods autonomously also increased (+12%).

The UX Challenge proved to be an **effective and scalable support scheme for SMEs**. It was successfully replicated and managed by various innovation intermediaries such as technology transfer foundations, public innovation agencies, business development agencies, and science parks across different economic and policy settings.

ELEMENTS OF AN INNOVATION CHALLENGE

Innovation Contests and Challenges have a number of elements or “**building blocks**” at their foundations, making it possible to function and generate the expected outcomes and impacts.

The [INNOCHALLENGE project](#) has created a **Visual Guide based on a Canvas tool** to help design tailored Innovation Challenges [14].

The Canvas is divided into **twelve blocks**, each representing a key component needed for a successful Innovation Challenge. The first set of blocks (“**WHY?**”) outlines the reasons for the Challenge, including problem identification, selection of participating companies, and expected outcomes. The middle blocks (“**WHAT?**”) focus on the activities required to achieve these results, detailing problem-solving tasks and roles of participants. The final set of blocks (“**HOW?**”) addresses the operational management of the Challenge, including planning and logistics.

This structured approach ensures that all aspects of an Innovation Challenge are thoroughly considered and effectively managed.

WHY?	WHAT?	HOW?
1. GOAL	5. ACTIVITIES	9. GOVERNANCE
2. SEEKERS	6. SOLVERS	10. BUSINESS MODEL
3. CHALLENGE	7. INCENTIVES	11. IPR
4. SOLUTIONS	8. TIMELINE	12. REGULATIONS

DOWNLOAD THE INNOVATION CHALLENGE DESIGN CANVAS HERE

THE INNOVATION CHALLENGE DESIGN CANVAS

Challenge Name _____

WHY?	WHAT?	HOW?
<p>1. GOAL</p> <p>Innovation Challenges are ran to support Open Innovation in SMEs. However, an innovation agency may also wish to achieve specific strategic goals via a Challenge. For example, a Challenge could be expected to impact both SMEs and other participants. Clarifying these strategic aspects at the very beginning is crucial in order to avoid problems down the road.</p>		
<p>2. SEEKERS</p> <p>Seekers are organizations (maybe more than one) that are facing one or more innovation problems and looking for answers. These might be the SMEs you want to support, or even Larger Enterprises (LE) you want to connect with SMEs. The seeker acts as "the client" of the initiative: the one who defines a specific problem or opportunity, and hopes to find some form of innovation via the Challenge.</p>		
<p>3. CHALLENGE</p> <p>This is the innovation issue that entices seekers to take part to the Innovation Challenge. It could be a technical problem with a production process, a design problem related to the development of a new product, or an aspect of business. A challenge may also offer an opportunity. The challenge is what solvers will actively work on in their "problem solving" activities.</p>		
<p>4. SOLUTIONS</p> <p>This is the usable value-adding result that the seeker hopes to obtain from the Challenge, which should be the solution to the innovation problem submitted by the seeker, or significant progress towards its solution. It is the main motivation for seekers taking part in the Challenge, and something they are prepared to pay for.</p>		

3. POSITIVE IMPACT CHALLENGE METHODOLOGY

BUILDING THE CHALLENGE MODEL:
FROM **INITIAL CONCEPTS** TO **FINAL DESIGN**

POSITIVE IMPACT CHALLENGE: BASIC WORKING MODEL

The POSITIVE Impact Challenge adapts the UX Challenge format to **better support social innovation actors**. This approach allows to enhance digitization within the social economy sector and prepares these actors to apply for innovation support funding. The graph below illustrates the basic working model of the POSITIVE Impact Challenge, showcasing the **value-adding process** from input to activities and finally to output. This model represents the foundational framework from which numerous iterations have been developed to better align with the specific needs and scope of social innovation projects. Through these refinements, the POSITIVE Impact Challenge has evolved to more effectively support SI actors in their pursuit of impactful social and technological advancements.

POSITIVE IMPACT CHALLENGE - DETAILED WORKING MODEL

The Innovation Challenge Design Canvas can be used to describe a detailed working model of the POSITIVE Impact Challenge.

The detailed model outlines the **type of seekers and projects** (or challenges) expected to participate: it also details the activities that solvers undertake to address the challenges, and clarifies the expected types of results (solutions).

Additionally, the use of the Canvas helps in **identifying potential beneficiaries**, their roles, and the necessary steps for the Challenge to succeed. For a visual representation of this application, see the Figure on the next page.

THE INNOVATION CHALLENGE DESIGN CANVAS

Challenge Name **POSITIVE IMPACT CHALLENGE**

WHY?	WHAT?	HOW?
<p>1. GOAL Innovation Challenges are ran to support Open Innovation in SMEs. However, an innovation agency may also wish to achieve specific strategic goals via a Challenge. For example, a Challenge could be expected to impact both SMEs and other participants. Clarifying these strategic aspects at the very beginning is crucial in order to avoid problems down the road.</p> <p>Stimulate collaborations between social innovation and tech innovation ecosystem players</p>		
<p>2. SEEKERS Seekers are organizations (maybe more than one) that are facing one or more innovation problems and looking for answers. These might be the SMEs you want to support, or even Larger Enterprises (LE) you want to connect with SMEs. The seeker acts as "the client" of the initiative: the one who defines a specific problem or opportunity, and hopes to find some form of innovation via the Challenge.</p> <p>Social businesses (social cooperatives, associations, non profits, etc.)</p>		
<p>3. CHALLENGE This is the innovation issue that entices seekers to take part to the Innovation Challenge. It could be a technical problem with a production process, a design problem related to the development of a new product, or an aspect of business. A challenge may also offer an opportunity. The challenge is what solvers will actively work on in their "problem solving" activities.</p> <p>Design or improve digital products and services more in line with user / customers' needs</p>		
<p>4. SOLUTIONS This is the usable value-adding result that the seeker hopes to obtain from the Challenge, which should be the solution to the innovation problem submitted by the seeker, or significant progress towards its solution. It is the main motivation for seekers taking part in the Challenge, and something they are prepared to pay for.</p> <p>Interactive GUI - Graphical User Interface prototype, scenarios, user journey maps, etc.</p>		

FOCUS ON BLOCKS 2 “SEEKERS” AND 4 “SOLUTIONS”

2. SEEKERS

In the POSITIVE Impact Challenge, seekers are selected via a public call for selection managed by one organizer. It is important to choose seekers based on key factors to align with the Challenge's goals. Key selection factors may include:

Key factors:

- **Legal form:** types such as cooperatives, social enterprises, B corporation, as well as limited companies.
- **Sector:** includes areas such as elder care, refugees, poverty, education, health, environment, and more.
- **Size:** avoid too small businesses unless they are innovative startups.
- **Urgency:** ensure businesses have the capacity and interest to invest in digital innovation.
- **R&D and innovation readiness:** seekers should have some prior experience with digital innovation projects.
- **Geographic reach:** preferably located near project partners for easier collaboration.

4. SOLUTIONS

The diagram below shows a range of possible solutions a seeker could receive at the end of the POSITIVE Impact Challenge: depending from the maturity of the challenge and the digital innovation project that it regards, solutions may be more or less tangible and mature.

FOCUS ON BLOCK 5 “ACTIVITIES”

5. ACTIVITIES

THE DESIGN SPRINT

The POSITIVE Impact Challenge employs the Design Sprint as its core method to get from challenges to solutions.

The Design Sprint is an agile product development method based on five phases that allows to deliver tangible solutions to digital product development issues in one week or less.

The Sprint allows product development teams to focus on the problem (1), ideate potential solutions in a visual manner (2), optimize the decision making process (3), employ rapid prototyping methods (4) and test the developed prototypes with users and customers (5) [13].

<https://sprintstories.com/7-tips-for-the-first-ever-design-sprint-of-a-company-16682b307c1c>

FOCUS ON BLOCK 5 “ACTIVITIES”

SCOPE OF ACTIVITIES

The refined model for the POSITIVE Impact Challenge also provide a more clear description of the scope of activity and type of work that can be addressed with the Design Sprint. This mainly depends on the goals of the seekers, and on the profile of the projects (or challenges) that enter the Challenge. In particular, the **scope of work mainly depends on two dimensions**:

Type of innovation:

- **Incremental Innovation:** the challenge involves improving existing products or services using user-centered methods (e.g., design thinking, user research).
- **Radical Innovation:** the challenge involves creating new products or services or making significant changes using to existing ones embedding advanced technologies (e.g., AR - Augmented Reality, IoT - Internet of Things).

Object of challenge:

- **Product:** the challenge involves innovating tangible products with digital features such as mobile apps, web apps, software, as well as consumer goods with GUIs - Graphical User Interfaces.
- **Service:** the challenge involves innovating services and related front-end processes having digital interaction touchpoints (e.g. online services).

The matrix on the next page illustrates how these two dimensions generate a space catering from different types of needs, projects, and challenges that the POSITIVE Impact Challenge can address. You can **use the examples in the matrix to help identify suitable seekers and challenges**. Notice that challenges marked in dark blue are not appropriate for the POSITIVE Impact Challenge due to scope or feasibility concerns.

<p>OBJECT OF CHALLENGE</p> <p>TYPE OF INNOVATION</p>	<p>PRODUCT</p>	<p>SERVICE</p>
<p>INCREMENTAL INNOVATION</p>	<p>Optimize the usability of a mobile app used by caregivers to allow them to spend more time with the supported older adults.</p> <p>Design a screen dashboard to be installed in the lobby of a nursery school communicating at a glance the key facts of the day for a given child.</p>	<p>Optimize the customer journey of an upcycling business and e-commerce (offering second-hand garments against the purchase of upcycled goods).</p> <p>A robot with vocal command to guide a wheelchair (too complex system to be addressed in the Challenge)</p> <p>An augmented reality and gamified solution to increase awareness about cultural heritage in young people (too complex system to be addressed in the Challenge)</p>
<p>RADICAL INNOVATION</p>	<p>Explore possible applications of AR (augmented reality) for developing a device for combating cognitive decline in older adults.</p> <p>Table-based app + sensors to help disabled girls living alone to manage time and routine activities (e.g., 1 hour showers).</p> <p>QR code-alike based mobile app to support sight impaired people in the use of public transport or other everyday services (e.g., supermarket).</p>	<p>Sensorization of desks at a co-working space to better profile customer segments, use models, tailor pricing, and optimize use of resources.</p> <p>Tele monitoring service of older adults to informal caregivers based on home sensing (Ambient Assisted Living).</p> <p>A system for optimizing energy consumption in households used by disabled people (too complex system to be addressed in the Challenge)</p>

POSITIVE IMPACT CHALLENGE: PHASES AND ACTION POINTS

4. EXAMPLES OF PROJECTS

EXPLORING **EXAMPLES** OF SOLUTIONS GENERATED BY THE POSITIVE IMPACT **CHALLENGE**

EXAMPLES FROM THE POSITIVE IMPACT CHALLENGE

From February to April 2024, three editions of the POSITIVE Impact Challenge were held in Germany, Italy, and Lithuania. In each country, a pair of technology and social partners implemented the Challenge model to support local social entrepreneurs and businesses.

CHALLENGE AND SOLUTIONS

This section presents nine successful fact sheets—three from each participating country—that describe the challenges submitted by social enterprises and the innovative solutions developed by teams of young talents, known as solvers.

IMPACT OF THE CHALLENGE

The showcased solutions highlight how effective teamwork, user-centered design and design thinking can lead to impactful improvements in addressing social challenges. By leveraging the POSITIVE Impact Challenge model, the initiative demonstrates the potential for collaborative efforts to foster positive social outcomes and drive innovation.

CASE #1

MOBILE APP FOR MONITORING WORK INTEGRATION PROJECTS

SEEKER	NAME: ALPI	TYPE: Social Cooperative
	URL: www.coop-alpi.it	CONTACT: Elisa Poletti
	MISSION: ALPI, which stands for "Avviamento al Lavoro su Progetti Individualizzati" (<i>Initiation to Work through Individualized Projects</i>), is a social cooperative enterprise that has been offering employment insertion pathways in Trentino since 1990.	
	TARGET GROUPS: People in vulnerable circumstances.	
CHALLENGE	To improve the User Experience of the MIO TUTOR Application , along with increasing its usability and utility. The App is a tool currently used within the cooperative by operators and team leaders to facilitate, streamline, and make observations, monitoring, and evaluation of employment insertion projects more objective.	
SOLUTION	The team of the challenge investigated reasons for scarce utilization of the app and identified usability and utility issues (mention product); it redesigned its main information architecture and user flows and delivered an interactive prototype on Figma.	
NEXT STEPS	ALPI is currently searching for project partners (designer + developer) and resources to refine the delivered prototype and developing a new version of the app.	
IMPACT	The use of the new app will allow the company to completely track the process of integration of a disadvantaged worker, and with that to better manage the process, report and account for yearly KPIs and achievement to the service owner (Public Services) and to explore artificial intelligence driven solutions (e.g., DSS). The app will also allow the tutor to focus on his coaching role.	

CASE #2

UPGRADING “DOMOTIC” TECH FOR PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

SEEKER	NAME: CS4	TYPE: Social Cooperative
	URL: https://www.cs4.coop/	CONTACT: Novella Eccel
	MISSION: Non-profit social cooperative founded in 1988, dedicated to providing daily support to people with disabilities and their families.	
	TARGET GROUPS: People with disabilities.	
CHALLENGE	The cooperative helps people with disabilities to achieve housing autonomy, through “domotic” flats. Yet the current technology (a wall screen) is outdated and unused. CS4 asked the team to replace it with a mobile app for easier, portable daily activities via smartphones.	
SOLUTION	Prior to prototyping, operator interviews informed the design process. User personas and scenarios were developed from the insights gathered. The proposed mobile app “Abitare” features separate interfaces for occupants and operators and syncs data with existing Microsoft accounts used by the cooperative.	
NEXT STEPS	The application can be developed by leveraging Microsoft Office APIs. The project aligns with the interests of other cooperatives operating in similar fields, and our intention is to collectively apply for national funding opportunities that support such initiatives.	
IMPACT	Reduction of service-related costs, a better integration with users’ daily routines and the possibility to remotely manage and update to do lists and calendars.	

CASE #3

CONNECTING CARE: A COMPREHENSIVE TECH SOLUTION

SEEKER	NAME: LA RETE	TYPE: Social Cooperative
	URL: https://la-rete.mailchimpsites.com/	CONTACT: Nicholas Moser
	MISSION: Since 1988, La Rete has been working with and for people with disabilities and their families to improve their quality of life, recognizing the community as a crucial place for social inclusion.	
	TARGET GROUPS: People with disabilities, their families and the community where they live.	
CHALLENGE	The organization wants to enhance user engagement through innovative website features . With profiles accessible to families, social workers, and administrators, our aim is to streamline communication, optimize tools, and centralize information.	
SOLUTION	The solution consists of a mobile app for operators, parents, and volunteers, along with a web app for operators. The operator's app includes an activity calendar, report submission, absence reporting, social folder access, and a photo archive. The parent's app offers activity tracking, contact lists, and document storage. The volunteer's app features note-taking, a photo archive, and activity booking.	
NEXT STEPS	Some students are exploring the project in their thesis. La Rete wants to develop the mobile app and is looking for resources that could support this phase.	
IMPACT	Sharp reduction in operator's time spent on phone calls or emailing to organize user activities will lead to more time spent directly with users and a better service offered.	

CASE #4

GREEN LOGISTICS OF NORTHERN LITHUANIA

SEEKER	NAME: Būk su manimi & Dirbinyčia	TYPE: Nonprofit organisation
	URL: https://www.facebook.com/Buk.su.manimi	CONTACT: Almante & Jolita
	MISSION: Significant reduction of textile waste (tons of textiles given a new life as attractive and useful products). Contribute to reduction of numbers of lonely elderly people, engage and integrate communities. Provide access to affordable, attractive goods made from recycled or renewed materials.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Marginalized / vulnerable people in the local community; consumers.	
CHALLENGE	Create a tool for charting faster and more efficient route, saving fuel and reducing CO2 emissions and using time more efficiently, during collection of discarded textiles, as well as household items within a 200-300 km radius from the town of Mazeikiai (Seeker's HQ).	
SOLUTION	A digital solution, Green Logistics of Northern Lithuania, to enable consistent routing: SE enters data (date and time for pick-up, number of textiles & other items to be collected, phone # & address) and receives route suggestion and fuel calculations depending on the vehicle they intend to use.	
NEXT STEPS	To perfect "Green Logistics of Northern Lithuania", the solution could be integrated with the SE's social media account where textile recollection requests are received on a regular basis, namely a bit of automation instead of manual entry of data.	
IMPACT	The specific impact of the innovation will be on smoother operations by the SE Būk su manimi & Dirbinyčia: specifically, digitalization and greening of SE's operations. Meanwhile, the overall societal impact will be the transformation of beliefs, habits and practices through education, engagement of youth, integration of the elderly, community creation and reduction of consumerism.	

CASE #5

ONE-STOP-SHOP PLATFORM TEXTALE

SEEKER	NAME: TEXTALE (Resursai tvariai plėtrai)	TYPE: Nonprofit organisation
	URL: https://textale.lt/	CONTACT: Viktorija Nausėdė
	MISSION: "TEXTALE" is a fashion resale and exchange platform that invites you to buy, sell or donate non-wearable but stylish and high-quality clothing, accessories, footwear and home textiles.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Residents who donate and sell their discarded clothing, other clothing items and textiles, as well as residents who volunteer and otherwise contribute to activities to reduce excess consumption.	
CHALLENGE	The challenge is to identify a comprehensive (physical and digital) C2B, C2B2C, and B2B solution that allows to meet the needs of various stakeholders – consumers, clothing brands, retailers and providers of relevant service providers to participate comfortably in the circular economy.	
SOLUTION	The TEXTALE client loyalty platform is designed for purchasing goods and services through TEXTALE's online and physical outlets, partner stores, and service outlets, offering special discounts and the possibility to pay with accumulated points. TEXTALE platform serves as an integrated Circular Economy solution encompassing activities from selling/donating to cleaning and repairing clothing and other textile items, reselling/ordering other essential services.	
NEXT STEPS	The Seeker is working with a team of IT and marketing experts and is seeking funding to complete, test and implement the TEXTALE platform Solution.	
IMPACT	TEXTALE one stop shop means new opportunities for the environment and people. The impact of this social innovation will be the normalization of Circular Economy practices and mainstreaming them into everyday lives of Lithuanians. Moreover, it will transform society's attitudes towards fashion.	

CASE #6

DIGITAL CASH CHANGE CALCULATOR

SEEKER	NAME: MB Solidari erdvė „Solidarumo kava“	TYPE: Small Partnership
	URL: https://www.facebook.com/Solidarikava	CONTACT: Ieva Karulaitienė
	MISSION: The social business is dedicated to integrating individuals with intellectual disabilities into the labor market by operating a mobile coffee bar across Lithuania with a coffee tricycle. Hot drinks and delicious desserts are served to provide a tasting experience and promote the message that individuals with disabilities are equal participants, uniquely special in their own right.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Youth with intellectual disability.	
CHALLENGE	A team of baristas with intellectual disabilities encounters difficulty in accurately returning change to customers who pay in cash. The need is for a semi-automated system (not self-checkout) that supports these young baristas to interact with clients and handle transactions effectively.	
SOLUTION	The solution consists of a digital cash change calculator which helps to identify and count cash. Such a solution empowers and enables a person with intellectual disability to be independent in "live" sales and cash handling without "taking them out of the equation".	
NEXT STEPS	The further development and implementation of this innovation will take place in the format of the SB2G business model, i.e. in partnership with the local authorities responsible for youth labor integration. The next steps include using the solution in stationery and mobile cafés.	
IMPACT	The solution prevents the risk of replacing baristas with a self-checkout counter. The primary impact is that workers with disabilities can participate in the entire service process while maintaining independence in task execution, supported by technology.	

CASE #7

ENHANCING A MOBILE APP FOR NEIGHBOURLY HELP

SEEKER	NAME: HILVER	TYPE: Social Startup
	URL: www.hilver.de	CONTACT: Nicolas Walter
	MISSION: HILVER offers a platform to volunteer and help older people with everyday tasks on the one hand, and to make use of help as a person in need of support on the other.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Senior citizens and other people in need of support; volunteers who help them.	
CHALLENGE	Users of the HILVER app, both those seeking and those providing help, should be encouraged to use it more intensively. Above all, older people should lose their fear of contact with the app and, secondly, helpers should accept more orders.	
SOLUTION	The solver team suggested merging the two existing Hilver apps (one for persons seeking, one for persons offering help) into one, thereby decreasing the confusion of users. Secondly, they proposed “Onboarding Events” for Seniors to reduce fear of contact. Thirdly, they introduced the AI-Assistant “HILVA” to lead users through the app. Lastly, a filter-function, reward system and gamification enhanced the user experience and engagement.	
NEXT STEPS	The first solution (web version) is almost complete. The other ideas (registration, filter function) are next on the priority list. The plan is not to implement the ideas one-to-one, as work is still required to integrate them into the existing product or to refine them.	
IMPACT	It is emphasized that these ideas would not have been developed without the incentive of the students and represent a significant enrichment . In general, there is a high level of satisfaction with the quality , and it is stated that expectations have been exceeded. Initial feedback on the web version has been extremely positive , which further strengthens confidence in the product.	

CASE #8

MOBILE APP FOR SCHEDULING APPOINTMENTS BETWEEN PEOPLE WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENTS AND SIGN LANGUAGE INTERPRETERS

SEEKER	NAME: OnDa	TYPE: Social StartUp
	URL: www.bfk.one	CONTACT: Fabian Hatwagner
	MISSION: Breaking down communication barriers for hearing-impaired and deaf-blind people and to developing solutions together with other associations, self-help groups and companies.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Hearing-impaired and sign language interpreters.	
CHALLENGE	Everyday communication between hearing, hearing-impaired, and deaf-blind people often requires translation by sign language interpreters. A digital booking system for in-person translation services should make it easier and more flexible to find and book appointments.	
SOLUTION	The solver team developed an All-In-One App that features standardized and organized appointment scheduling with two interfaces: one for interpreters and one for the hearing impaired, which is specifically inclusively designed.	
NEXT STEPS	The next aim is to implement a billing function. Invoice templates are to be stored, accessibility ensured, and interpreter profiles implemented. Also, an optional function is to save specific interpreters as "favorites" that along with the option to create series of appointments should improve the user experience in the future.	
IMPACT	This solution might be the first in Europe: Around 70 million people in Europe live with hearing impairments.	

CASE #9

BOOKING TOOL FOR SCHOOLS

SEEKER	NAME: pro familia	TYPE: Welfare association
	URL: www.profamilia.de/fachinfos/fachveranstaltungen	CONTACT: Eva Rebholz
	MISSION: Early sexual education has been proven to prevent individual and social problems. pro familia offers needs-oriented, individualized and professional workshops for schools.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Schools (teachers).	
CHALLENGE	An online booking tool is intended to make it easier for schools to book appointments and put together customized content (modular principle from the pro familia's offers). The aim is to make booking easier, faster and clearer. This should save internal resources.	
SOLUTION	The solver team developed a click dummy for a booking tool for both target groups: teachers and the pro familia employees . It includes the choice of offers, scheduling of appointments, booking section, and invoicing.	
NEXT STEPS	Implement the concept of the problem solution by finding a way to apply the desired functions using the basic MS office package. This will make the solution scalable and applicable in all sites without requiring extra software.	
IMPACT	The click dummy itself produced by the team is less important, as it mainly represents an implementation option. The concept of the problem solution behind it has a much greater value from the organisation's perspective. As a social organization with little money available for IT, pro familia are dependent on support. Taking part in a hackathon can be a great solution to this problem.	

5. HINTS AND TIPS FOR A SUCCESSFUL CHALLENGE

EVERYTHING YOU NEED TO KNOW TO **ACTIVATE** THE POSITIVE IMPACT **CHALLENGE** IN YOUR ECOSYSTEM

1. PREPARATION

2. PROMOTION

3. SET-UP

4. EXECUTION

5. CONCLUSION

PHASE 1: PREPARATION

- [Phase 0: Make sure to have a **sound working model** to implement the Challenge: use the Innovation Challenge Design Canvas].
- Ensure your team has the expertise to handle legal documents (e.g. calls for selection of participants) and GDPR compliance.
- Build partnerships with stakeholders, especially universities, for effective promotion and governance.
- Clearly assign roles and responsibilities internally to streamline communication, decision-making, and execution.
- Identify members for evaluation committees to select participants (both solvers and seekers) and assess results at the final event.
- Secure sponsors for the Challenge, if required (e.g. offering prizes for solvers).

1. PREPARATION

2. PROMOTION

3. SET-UP

4. EXECUTION

5. CONCLUSION

PHASE 2: PROMOTION

- Develop strong marketing and communication strategies to reach key targets, including students and social innovation actors.
- Craft tailored messaging for different target groups to clearly communicate the event's value and encourage participation.
- Ensure Challenge partners establish a promotional funnel and an efficient process for managing applications, especially from seekers.
- Balance the number of applications to avoid overbooking and potential frustrations. Aim for a manageable volume (e.g. 5 seekers maximum).
- Engage directly with students on campus by promoting the challenge at lectures, events, and other activities.
- Introduce the Challenge concept to seekers, building trust and interest in the event and its methodology.
- Recruit experienced mentors with relevant expertise to guide solver teams during the event.

1. PREPARATION

2. PROMOTION

3. SET-UP

4. EXECUTION

5. CONCLUSION

PHASE 3: SET UP

- Identify in advance criteria utilized to create efficient teams.
- Create diverse teams with varied skills to approach challenges creatively and effectively.
- Ensure solvers understand their accountability and responsibilities throughout the Challenge.
- Provide training for solvers (e.g. on the Design Sprint methodology) well in advance so they can perform all tasks independently by the Challenge start.
- Schedule a preparatory meeting with seekers to prepare for the kick-off event. The purpose is to make sure that the company can present the challenge independently during the bilateral meeting and provide all the information to start the activities.
- Create a detailed challenge brief (description of the challenge) and share it with participants, making it accessible in a shared work environment (e.g. Google Drive)
- Pay attention to logistical details such as venue selection, equipment setup, and transportation to ensure a smooth event experience.
- Prepare comprehensive online collaboration environments (e.g. Miro/Mural boards) with all explanations and answers to potential questions, as well as embedding a template of the methodology (e.g. Design Sprint phases).
- Ensure expert mentors familiarize themselves with methods on the Miro/Mural and their specific challenge.
- Confirm that seekers provide all necessary materials and are available for interactions with solvers.

1. PREPARATION

2. PROMOTION

3. SET-UP

4. EXECUTION

5. CONCLUSION

PHASE 4: EXECUTION

- Kick-off meeting: prepare the participants well in advance, this meeting is key to enable collaboration between solvers, seekers and mentors.
- Organize a daily monitoring activity to check what teams have done the day before and plan to do the present day (ex. stand-up meeting with team leaders).
- Alternatively to the previous two points, perform daily check-ins with mentors and solvers, including detailed discussions on methods and progress; consider half-day check-ups if necessary.
- Consider to update (yet not disrupt) the scope of the challenge in case issues arise (e.g. too broad scope, too complex challenge, missing information from the seeker's side).
- Perform quick checks with mentors via WhatsApp or phone calls for immediate updates and support.
- Remain flexible and adapt to changing circumstances or unexpected challenges, adjusting the event schedule or activities as needed.

1. PREPARATION

2. PROMOTION

3. SET-UP

4. EXECUTION

5. CONCLUSION

PHASE 5: CONCLUSION

- Make sure you have a sound method and process to evaluate the results and assign the prizes / incentives. This shall be clarified in the call for selection of solvers in advance.
- Include a high-level jury to boost solvers' motivation and enhance publicity.
- Plan the final event months in advance to ensure that a larger public joins and for a smooth execution, including media coverage.
- Organize communication follow-up actions, such as press releases, to promote outcomes and maintain visibility.
- Evaluate the satisfaction of participating companies and gather feedback from solvers, mentors, judges, and sponsors within one month of the event's conclusion.
- Try to monitor and support the capability of seekers to exploit and industrialize the Challenge results (solutions) as this will allow to achieve expected outcomes and impacts.

TIPS FROM PARTNERS

When planning a hackathon for students, it's crucial to communicate clearly and engage them effectively. Speak their language and make announcements and check-ins exciting. Start the day with clear goals so everyone knows what to work towards. Schedule an energizing break at midday to keep spirits high. End with a fun check-out where participants can share their experiences. These tips will make your hackathon productive and memorable!

VIVIEN RIENER, PROJECT
MANAGER, GH

BEATRICE DEVIGILI,
INNOVATION OFFICER, HIT

Engaging seekers is crucial for the Challenge's success. Thoroughly evaluating applications and selecting feasible solutions ensures high chances of implementation. Proper alignment and groundwork with seekers during the promotion phase are essential, as it sets clear goals and prepares the ground for solvers to effectively tackle the challenges.

To make your open innovation challenge a success, focus on creating a relaxed and welcoming environment where collaboration thrives. Clear communication and exciting goals will keep participants motivated and engaged, while regular check-ins and feedback help them stay on track. Support their creativity with resources and encourage them to think outside the box, fostering an atmosphere where bold, disruptive ideas can emerge. With the right energy, teamwork, and structure, you'll empower participants to deliver impactful solutions that push the boundaries of innovation.

INGA VYŠNIAUSKIENĖ,
HEAD OF
COMMUNICATIONS, LIC

TIPS FROM PARTNERS

Foster a collaborative environment by engaging a diverse group of participants, including community members, industry experts, and potential end-users, to ensure a wide range of perspectives and solutions. Encourage continuous feedback and iteration loop by providing clear guidelines, structured workshops, and access to resources, enabling participants to refine their ideas and address real-world challenges effectively.

**VIKTORIJA BRAŽIŪNAITĒ,
DIRECTOR, LISVA**

**MIRJAM ZILLOBER,
PROJECT CONSULTANT,
SEZ**

Collaborate with applied university courses to create a win-win situation: Students can apply their skills to tackle real social problems, while earning ECTS points and getting technical guidance. Ensure a diverse mix of students from different backgrounds for creative and effective problem-solving.

**CLAUDIO TAGLIABUE,
CO-FOUNDER, TST**

Start with a smile! To achieve good results, everyone must collaborate effectively and think outside the box. Create a collaborative, convivial, and welcoming environment: you will enhance teamwork and creativity and set the field up for disruptive ideas.

6. HOW TO MAXIMIZE THE IMPACT OF THE CHALLENGE

A ROADMAP FOR INTERLINKING **SOCIAL** INNOVATION
AND **TECHNOLOGY** INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

STRENGTHENING ECOSYSTEM CONNECTIONS

Building **sustainable relationships among stakeholders** is crucial for linking social innovation and technology innovation ecosystems regionally and internationally. Such relationships foster long-term collaboration at both regional and European levels.

Regional Networking Workshops (RNW), or other **ecosystem-building events**, can facilitate this connection. These workshops bring together stakeholders from both ecosystems to identify common interests, needs, and opportunities for collaboration. The workshops are finalized to conclude with the creation of a **regional roadmap** that outlines the current state of ecosystem integration and suggests actions for further cooperation, including potential Memorandums of Understanding (MOU). The insights gained from the workshop and the resulting roadmap are vital for crafting targeted policy recommendations that address stakeholders' needs and support ecosystem integration.

The POSITIVE Impact Challenge, an open innovation tool, supports innovation and digitization in social enterprises. Workshops and roadmap creation produced during the POSITIVE project explored how this model can be replicated to boost collaboration and innovation across similar ecosystems and connected stakeholders by engaging them in planning the impact-driven actions.

In the next pages, this Playbook provides a **template for creating an effective roadmap** to connect social and technology innovation ecosystems with a regional focus.

ROADMAP DEVELOPMENT STEPS

This table outlines key milestones on the left for building a regional roadmap that links social innovation (SI) and tech innovation (TI) ecosystems. On the right are step-by-step instructions for defining cooperation themes, recording stakeholder commitments, and planning actionable steps.

MILESTONE TITLE & ACTIVITY DETAILS	COMMENTS AND SUGGESTIONS
<p>TOPICS AND PRINCIPLES: Define principles and parameters, as well as Topics for cooperation:</p> <p><i>Topic 1. ...</i> <i>Topic 2. ... etc.</i></p>	<p>Begin by detailing the tasks and activities planned for this phase, starting with the date of your Regional Networking Workshop (RNW). This can be a comprehensive description or a simple list of activities.</p>
<p>CONNECT WITH STAKEHOLDERS: Record the specific pledges and commitments made by each stakeholder.</p> <p><i>Stakeholder 1, pledge x/y/...</i> <i>Stakeholder 2, commits x/y/ ...</i></p>	<p>At the respective RNW, inform stakeholders that the Roadmap will be made public, thus "Putting on the Record" the regional ecosystem stakeholders & their commitments/pledges related to interlinking SI & TI ecosystems.</p>
<p>INPUT FROM WORKSHOPS AND CHALLENGES: Outline agreed-upon actions, including any upcoming Impact Challenge events.</p> <p><i>Action 1.1</i> <i>Action 2.1</i> <i>Action 3.1</i></p>	<p>After the RNW, circulate the revised list of actions and commitments / pledges. Make adjustments & changes: meet with stakeholders to debrief and revise regional SI-TI ecosystem stakeholders and their commitments (pledges).</p>
<p>EVALUATE PROGRESS: Finalize formal agreements such as MOUs or similar documents to contain revised further action or follow-up:</p> <p><i>Action 1.2v</i> <i>Action 2.2v</i> <i>Action 3.2v</i></p>	<p>Check-in with stakeholders - both existing and new - via e-mail or short online meeting. Discuss their progress with commitments/pledges and make necessary adjustments to the Roadmap or the detailed action plan/s based on the Roadmap.</p>
<p>ADJUST, DESIGN & ITERATE: Revise and lock-in commitments for further actions & activities.</p>	<p>Announce outcomes! Share the results and impact of the collaboration. Highlight the achievements and explore new opportunities for further interlinking the ecosystems.</p>

THE IDEAL ROADMAP FOR INTERLINKING ECOSYSTEMS

INITIAL POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CREATING A SUPPORTIVE POLICY ENVIRONMENT

1

FOSTER KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE AND CAPACITY BUILDING

- **Targeted Training:** Develop and implement training programs that enhance digital literacy in social enterprises. These programs focusing on practical technology applications to bridge the gap between traditional practices and modern digital tools, would enhance the impact of the challenges within the social innovation ecosystems.
- **Higher Education Integration:** Encourage the inclusion of social innovation subjects and topics in higher education curricula. The potential benefits of such initiatives would be those of exposing students to real-world challenges while providing fresh insights to social enterprises. Moreover, while the Design Sprint is a week-long endeavour, the complete and full impact challenge methodology-based “Technology-enabled Social Innovation” course is easy to convert into a module or semester-long elective. Finally on the same point, the benefits of such approach would be felt on social enterprise, university, local and regional levels all at once.

2

PROMOTE COLLABORATION AND NETWORKING

- **Regional Hubs:** Establish regional and thematic hubs to connect social and technology innovators. These platforms could facilitate collaboration and act as catalysts for cross-ecosystem partnerships, fostering innovation.
- **Public - Private Partnerships:** Encourage partnerships between social enterprises, technology innovators, and public institutions to leverage shared resources and expertise. Such collaborations are crucial for addressing complex societal challenges, like expanding and mainstreaming circular economy practices or achieving the UN SDGs.

3

ENHANCE ACCESS TO FINANCE AND RESOURCES

- **Impact - Focused Funding:** Develop financial instruments, such as impact investment funds, that specifically target social enterprises using technology. Funding and supports are essential for any R&D activity, including Open Innovation which has the greatest potential for creating inclusive, digital, green or similar solutions.
- **Mentorship Programs:** Invest in mentorship to guide social entrepreneurs in business development and technology adoption, helping them navigate innovation ecosystems effectively. Mentors can offer guidance on impact measurement, ensuring sustainable growth.

4

STIMULATION OF SUPPLY AND DEMAND

- **Social Procurement:** Implement policies that prioritize social impact in public procurement, creating a market for innovative solutions. This can drive collaboration between social innovation ecosystems and technology innovation ecosystems.
- **Regulatory Sandboxes:** Establish environments where social enterprises can test new ideas without regulatory burdens, fostering experimentation and rapid innovation. This approach can accelerate the development of impactful solutions by creating safe legal spaces Open and Impactful Innovation.

CALL TO ACTION

We invite the Social Innovation and Technology Innovation Ecosystems stakeholders EU-wide to engage in co-creating policy recommendations, regional roadmaps and action plans mimicking the POSITIVE project but also going beyond it. Maximizing the impact of the challenge is up to us, the stakeholders. Maximizing the impact of the challenge is possible by bringing it into new jurisdictions, educational and geopolitical realities. Maximizing the impact of the challenge requires bringing in insights from diverse fields. Maximizing the impact of the challenge means addressing the local needs while maximizing global impact by collaborating across sectors and borders.

7. LET'S STAY IN TOUCH!

MEET THE PROJECT PARTNERS

SOCIAL PARTNERS

GRÜNHOF E.V.

Grünhof e.V. supports social innovation by assisting social startups & organizations in tackling societal challenges by providing consulting, coworking, workshops and a strong network.

 <https://gruenhof.org>

 vivien@gruenhof.org

LITHUANIAN SOCIAL BUSINESS ASSOCIATION

It is a national umbrella organization of social businesses, active in advocacy and policy making, as well as social enterprise capacity-building and ecosystem development activities.

 <https://lisva.org>

 viktorija.b@lisva.org

TRENTINO SOCIAL TANK

It was established as a business incubator that enhances and develops new ideas with a focus on the welfare, personal services and social economy sectors.

 <https://www.trentinosocialtank.it>

 claudio.tagliabue@trentinosocialtank.it

TECH PARTNERS

FONDAZIONE HUB INNOVAZIONE TRENINO

Instrumental body of the Autonomous Province of Trento, whose goal is to add value to research results by promoting the economic and social development of Trentino through dissemination and technology transfer activities.

 <https://www.trentinoinnovation.eu>

 b.devigili@trentinoinnovation.eu

LITHUANIAN INNOVATION CENTRE

LIC is a non-profit organization dedicated to fostering innovation across various sectors by offering innovation support services to enterprises, research institutions, industry associations, business support organizations, and public authorities both in Lithuania and abroad.

 <https://www.lic.lt>

 i.vysniauskiene@lic.lt

STEINBEIS EUROPA ZENTRUM

Operating in Baden-Württemberg, Germany, SEZ provides innovation consultancy with a focus on EU research funding and international markets.

 <https://www.steinbeis-europa.de/en/home>

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DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

This Playbook is based on the POSITIVE Deliverable D4.2 POSITIVE Impact Challenge toolkit including policy recommendations.

The deliverable and other Results of the POSITIVE project can be found at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101096390>

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 POSITIVE

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THE POSITIVE IMPACT CHALLENGE PLAYBOOK

